

**ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF COLAIZZI'S METHOD IN
QUALITATIVE STUDIES****Quimberly B. Lanos**

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ABSTRACT

Colaizzi's method is generally used among qualitative researches specifically in phenomenological researches. The method is structurally recognized in the body of researches as it provides comprehensive processes that enabled the researchers to extract actual responses based on the context and objectives of the research studies conducted. This study assessed the impact of Colaizzi's method in qualitative studies. This study employed sequential explanatory mixed method through the used of the developed survey-questionnaire and guide questions. It was participated by 150 public school teachers in the Philippines who were purposively selected. Findings of the study revealed that teachers as researchers and scholars show significant capabilities in using Colaizzi's method in qualitative studies as they recognize and understand the importance of Colaizzi's method involving familiarization, extraction, meaning generation, clustering of themes, describing phenomenon and validation. In addition, teachers assessed that Colaizzi's method posed difficulty in conducting qualitative studies in terms of depth of understanding, rigorous analysis and consistent participants' involvement throughout the research process. Further, teachers viewed Colaizzi's method as highly scientific method to extract meaning and generate relevant themes based on the research objectives which made qualitative data credible, reliable and scientific. The study proposed a training program that develop teachers' understanding and use of Colaizzi's method in writing qualitative studies.

Keywords:

Assess, impact, Colaizzi, method, qualitative, studies, scientific, rigorous, analysis

INTRODUCTION

Writing a research work is a tedious process because of the highly intricate processes it contains. Research as a systematic process involves a comprehensive and scientific manner of addressing problems based on the observed phenomena or conditions. In this line, one of the critical measures in the academic community is the administration of a research work. In educational context, the conduct of a research work helps school heads, teachers, learners, parents and other stakeholders to scientifically address the prevailing problems, concerns, issues and conditions that hamper the effective and efficient delivery of education. Research work in the field of education encompasses a bigger academic responsibility for teachers because of research's scientific value, teachers and other scholars in the field, can objectively measure the prevailing conditions and provide scientific answers for the problems they experienced or observed. As teachers are engaged in the conduct of research studies, they commonly use quantitative method specifically descriptive design in order to describe the conditions they observed and eventually, provide practical output that may help the system and the organization to address the identified problems. The credence and integrity of a research work depend largely on how the researchers select and use appropriate research methods. In several circumstances, teachers are more inclined in using quantitative methods because of its convenience and practicality on the basis that it holds lesser work compare to that qualitative studies. In this regard, one of the prevailing methods being used by teachers as they administer their research works is quantitative-descriptive method. On one hand, there are also great numbers of teachers who are also inclined in using qualitative studies particularly employing phenomenological and case

study design. Both of these designs are contained under the qualitative aspect. For teachers who are strongly engaged in the use of qualitative design, they only understand that interviews, focus-group discussions and case analysis based on conditions are merely based on interpreting the responses of their participants. Another concern exists as teachers used qualitative studies since they are less familiar the proper selection and use of Colaizzi's method as data analysis technique in qualitative studies particularly under phenomenological research design. As defined by Williams (2020), Colaizzi's structured approach serve as a foundational data analysis technique for phenomenological studies. Apparently, Colaizzi method also serves as a critical approach which emphasizes the importance of lived experiences of the subject participants under a certain research work.

As shown in the study of Praveena and Sasikumar (2021), steps under Colaizzi's method involves the reading-reading of transcripts which enable the researchers to obtain the general sense about the whole content. Thus, it follows by comprehensive extraction of statements that relate to the phenomenon and are based from the transcripts. Then, the researchers formulate meaning based from the extracted significant statements and proceeds to the organization of the formulated meanings so as to cluster major themes and subthemes. Thereafter, the researchers integrated the findings into an exhaustive description and lastly, such descriptions are fundamental to the research topic. Colaizzi's method of data analysis is a rigorous and robust and therefore, qualitative method that ensures the credibility and reliability of a research work's results. Researchers using Colaizzi's method considered a clear and logical process through which the fundamental structure could be explored (Wirihana et al., 2018). Colaizzi's strategy was effectively utilized in identifying significant statements from the transcribed verbatim and meanings. The formulated meanings clusters of themes and themes were derived which eventually helped the development of thematic map (Praveena & Sasikumar, 2021). Properly carrying Colaizzi's method in examining the lived experiences of the participants was an appropriate scientific process that helped researchers explain the situations and experiences of the participants under the nature and content of the study (Shahrad et al., 2024). Analysis and exemplar application using Colaizzi's method was grounded on a more intricate yet scientific structure that yielded credible and reliable qualitative results (Abalos et al., 2016).

The researchers observed that most teachers who are selecting qualitative method put less emphasis on the use of Colaizzi's method specially when they are conducting a phenomenological research. In addition, the researchers observed that because of failure in using such method, qualitative studies may compromised its credibility and reliability. So, these conditions influenced researchers' interests to assess the impact of colaizzi's method in qualitative studies specifically under the phenomenological researches conducted by public school teachers across the Philippines.

OBJECTIVES

This study assessed the impact of using Colaizzi's method in the conduct of qualitative studies made by public school teachers among the selected schools in the Philippines. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. How may the respondents' use of Colaizzi's method in the conduct of qualitative studies may be assessed in terms of familiarization, extraction, meaning generation, clustering of themes and phenomenon description and validation?
2. How may the respondents' assess their experiences as they employed Colaizzi's method in writing qualitative studies in terms of depth of understanding, analysis and participants' involvement?
3. What are the views of the respondents in using Colaizzi's method in writing qualitative studies?
4. Based from the findings, what proposed training program can be crafted?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed sequential explanatory mixed method in order to assess the impact of Colaizzi's method in the conduct of qualitative studies. Apparently, the study used a simple random sampling technique and selected the participation of 150 public school teachers among the selected public schools in the Philippines. Thus, the study used a researcher-made survey-questionnaire which served as the main instrument of the study while guide questions were used in the administration of structured interviews. As for the construction and validation of the developed survey-questionnaire, it contained two (2) parts. Part 1 contained items relating to the use of Colaizzi's method in the conduct of qualitative studies while part 2 contained items relating to the experiences of the respondents when Colaizzi's method was used. Apparently, the similar instrument was subjected to validation which was rated by three (3) experts in qualitative studies. As such, expert-validators marked the

developed survey-questionnaire as “outstanding.” Thereafter, the researchers subjected the same instrument to pilot testing where items under part 1 gained a Cronbach Alpha result of .817 which verbally described as “Acceptable.” On the other hand, items under part 2 obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of .791 which verbally described as “Acceptable.” Thus, the researchers used a 4-Likert Scale. On the other hand, the developed guide questions contained ten (10) questions which were inductively arranged by the researchers. The same was subjected to validation process whereas similar roster of experts was sought. Then, they marked the developed guide questions as “good.” In line formal administration of survey-questionnaire to quantify the quantitative aspect of the study, the researchers sent a Google Form link to the respondents’ personal email addresses. Then, they collected and organized the raw data gathered. On one hand, in the administration of structured interviews, the researchers only selected ten (10) teachers as participants for structured interview. They were subjected to formal interview using Zoom Teleconferencing. Each participant given 10-15 minutes then, their responses were encoded and transcribed by the researchers. All qualitative responses pertaining to the teachers’ views in the use of Colaizzi’s method were properly recorded and transcribed through the use of Table of Qualitative Responses (TQR). Thus, from the coded statements, the researchers extracted meanings and formulated the major themes and subthemes relating to the views of teachers in using Colaizzi’s method in conducting qualitative studies. Apparently, statistical tools were used to quantify the quantitative aspect of the study such as: frequency, mean and general weighted mean. These statistical tools were used in order to assess the respondents’ use of Colaizzi’s methods and their experiences in using such as they administer qualitative studies. On one hand, thematic analysis was used to generate themes and subthemes relating to the views of the respondents in using Colaizzi’s method in writing qualitative studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The use and application of Colaizzi’s method in the conduct of qualitative researches specifically phenomenological studies are commonly disregarded by teachers whereby they failed to comprehensively apply such method that directly inflict the credibility and reliability of qualitative data they gathered. Significance of understanding Colaizzi’s method in writing qualitative researches would enabled teachers as researchers to comprehensively extract the experiences and conditions as experienced by their participants. In this line, key elements were extracted as teachers used Colaizzi’s method which included the collection of data through interviews, transcription and careful analysis. The use of this method enabled teachers to provide deep immersion into their participants’ perspectives ensuring that the essence of their experiences were scientifically captured.

1. **Use of Colaizzi’s Method in the Conduct of Qualitative Studies.** The results showed that familiarization obtained the highest mean score of 3.78, described as strongly agree. Meanwhile, extraction gained a mean score of 3.56, described as strongly agree while meaning generation and clustering of themes and phenomenon both obtained mean scores of 3.48, both described as strongly agree. Then, description and validation gained a mean score of 3.42, described as agree. On familiarization, as this variable obtained the highest mean, this implied that teachers strongly agreed that they comprehensively recognized and immersed into the responses comprising the data gathered from their participants. This also signifies that teachers strongly agreed that with the data familiarization, they were able to understand the context and nuances of information they obtained from their participants as they conduct their qualitative research work. Meanwhile, the results on extraction showed that teachers strongly agreed that they valued the process of determining significant statements and insights from the data they obtained. Accordingly, the results also implied that teachers strongly agreed that extraction phase was essential groundwork for Colaizzi’s method in building key themes and patterns under the subject study. On one hand, the result of meaning generation and clustering of themes, it indicated that teachers strongly agreed that synthesis was also a fundamental yet critical step under Colaizzi’s method because it allowed them to generate meaning from the data before the comprehensive interpretation of findings relative to the nature of the qualitative study they undertake. Lastly, the result on description and validation, it implied that teachers strongly agreed that they acknowledged the importance of accuracy in the description and validation of findings. Thus, teachers also strongly agreed that effective description and validation were also critical to impose credibility and reliability of their findings in their qualitative studies. Results of the study supported the study of Vignato et al. (2022) which revealed that Colaizzi’s method directed qualitative researches into comprehensive, reliable and

credible work as it laid ground process for critical summation of statements or responses. The study implicated that Colaizzi's method was widely recognized approach in qualitative research. As such, this method emphasized a systematic process for analyzing qualitative data as assessed by teachers.

2. **Teachers' Experiences in the Use of Colaizzi's Method in Writing Qualitative Studies.** The results showed that depth of understanding gained the highest mean score of 3.92, described as strongly agree while analysis gained a mean score of 3.78, described as strongly agree. Lastly, the result also revealed that participants' involvement obtained a mean score of 3.56, described as strongly agree. The result on depth of understanding implied that teachers strongly agreed that Colaizzi's method significantly deepened their understanding on qualitative research. Also, the result indicated that teachers used Colaizzi's method in order to gain more profound insights into the experiences that their participants expressed. On one hand, the result on analysis aspect, teachers strongly agreed that they immensely appreciate the systematic nature of data analysis using the method. Apparently, the result further indicated that Colaizzi's method helped them to gain structured process helping them to identify key themes and patterns coherently. Lastly, the result on participants' involvement, teachers strongly agreed that their participants' engagement helped them enriched the data they needed and fostered strong relevance in which teachers obtained more insightful data as their participants were strongly engaged throughout the data collection process. Results of the study supported the study of Momesso (2019) which concluded that applying Colaizzi's method enabled the researchers to extract meaningful insights and obtained trustworthiness of the study conducted. Hence, the study implicated that teachers used Colaizzi's method in order to produce high-quality qualitative research which could inform educational practices contributing to the development of education and other related disciplines thereto.
3. **Teachers' Views in Using Colaizzi's Method in Writing Qualitative Studies.** The results showed that there were two (2) major themes extracted such as: Highly Scientific Method and Generate Relevant Themes based on Research Objectives. On *highly scientific method*, teachers viewed the use of Colaizzi's method as a rigorous framework for administering qualitative studies. Accordingly, the result also implied that teachers expressed that the structured nature of the method enhanced their research credibility and reliability of findings. Teachers also felt more confident in their research writing process as the method directed them scientifically so as to extract relevant statements thereby producing scientific rigor in their studies. As expressed by one of the participants:

"It helped me really to comprehensively analyze all my participants statements because of the process or steps which I needed to follow."

Another participant made mentioned that:

"Because of clear and precise process and flow that Colaizzi's method show, I could confidently say that my data analysis was on a right scientific track."

On the other hand, *on generation of relevant themes based on research objectives*, teachers viewed that Colaizzi's method reflect their personal inclination to their research work as they were able to produce meaningful discussions emanating from scientifically drawn statements from their participants. In addition, teachers' viewed the method as of great scientific help as they could facilitate proper determination and extraction of themes that directly meet their research objectives. Further, results also showed that teachers emphasized the relevance and reliability of findings were obtained through the use of the method as generation of themes made through it, addressed the nature, context and scope of their research work. Also, they were able to generate actionable insights which informed effective measures under the qualitative research work they were writing. As expressed by one of the participants:

"I really feel that all meanings and relevant expressions were scientifically extracted when I used Colaizzi's method."

Also, one participant shared that:

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“Whenever I used Colaizzi’s method, I am directed and not confused in analyzing the data I gathered leading me to relevance and accuracy of my research work.”

Results of the study supported the study of Gumarang Jr et al. (2021) which revealed that Colaizzi’s method was to generate an exhaustive description of phenomena addressing the established research questions. Thus, similar study showed that the method was particularly beneficial for correctly describing the problems and context that have been established in their research work.

4. **Proposed Training Program.** A proposed program was developed and titled as: Mastering Colaizzi’s Method Grounded on Education-Related Researches. This training program aims to provide teachers as participants with a comprehensive understanding of Colaizzi’s method through the developed module containing inputs and practical exercises. It will be participated by teachers, school heads and selected stakeholders. Also, this program aims to develop teachers’ ability and competence to analyze qualitative data and extract meaningful insights using the method. There be a 2-day training aligned with the aforesaid objectives. For day 1, it will contain activities such as lecture, discussions and workshops which covers an overview about Colaizzi’s method. Day 2 will cover the actual use of the method by incorporating significant elements such as familiarization to extraction. Funds to be used would be subjected to the availability of school funds.

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CONCLUSION

The use of this method enabled teachers to provide deep immersion into their participants’ perspectives ensuring that the essence of their experiences were scientifically captured. Teachers as researchers and scholars show significant capabilities in using Colaizzi’s method in qualitative studies as they recognize and understand the importance of Colaizzi’s method involving familiarization, extraction, meaning generation, clustering of themes, describing phenomenon and validation. In addition, teachers assessed that Colaizzi’s method posed difficulty in conducting qualitative studies in terms of depth of understanding, rigorous analysis and consistent participants’ involvement throughout the research process. Further, teachers viewed Colaizzi’s method as highly scientific method to extract meaning and generate relevant themes based on the research objectives which made qualitative data credible, reliable and scientific. The study proposed a training program that develop teachers’ understanding and use of Colaizzi’s method in writing qualitative studies.

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